

Erlitou (Ritual/Ceremonial/Palatial Districts)

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The site of Erlitou is one of the most important sites for the study of the Bronze Age in central China (1800 BCE – 206 BCE). It was discovered by the well-known archaeologist Xu Xusheng in 1959, who led a team in search of the Xia capitals based on the later historical texts. Decades of excavations have yielded tremendously rich amounts of material remains, offering first-hand data for the analysis of the early development of technology, religion, social evolution, long-distance cultural communication and other key aspects of the Central Plains of China. It is often regarded as the beginning of the Bronze Age in central China, although bronze metallurgy was introduced via the Eurasia Steppe and performed in China in much earlier periods in the north and northwest. More importantly, it was Erlitou people who combined the newly arrived metallurgy with the long extant ceramic vessels and invented bronze ritual vessels, which distinguished China from all other parts of Eurasia and dominated the Chinese Bronze Age for nearly two thousand years. The abstract animal faces on these bronze ritual vessels, together with jades, dragon-shaped sceptres decorated with turquoise and other exotic objects or materials, indicates the presence of supernatural beings in the perception of the Erlitou people. Further indication comes from the large amount of human and animal sacrifices, sometimes neatly arranged in the ceremonial pits. There is also evidence of divination, which used the cracks that resulted from firing the animal bones to predict the future, a tradition that was inherited from the late Neolithic periods and continued to the late Shang Anyang when oracle bones were widely discovered. Despite a range of archaeological features indicative of potential religious activities and thoughts, it remains ambiguous as to which part of Erlitou was dedicated to religion. Recent excavations reveal clear urban planning at Erlitou. The entire site (ca. 3 km²) had been divided into nine sections by two north-south roads and two east-west roads crossed with each other. Along the central north-south line, which becomes the one most important land marker in urban designing in later Chinese dynasties, lay the ritual/ceremonial section, palatial section and craft section. Therefore, as indicated by quite a few mounds and circular altars, the central north of Erlitou appears likely to be a centre for ritual/religious activities, involving worshiping or mass gathering. It is also worthy pointing out that other areas such as palatial section could also been involved with religion, where one can find some tombs with special burial practice. Given the massive scale of organization and many pioneering achievements at Erlitou, there is probably no doubt that the ritual system played a critical part, within which a number of elements could be related to religion. Unfortunately, no sign of writing has yet been recovered, making it very challenging to distinguish ritual with religion or perform finer-grained research on various aspects of religion at Erlitou. Most of our observation or answers in the rest of the database will be originated to the ritual/ceremonial section of Erlitou, since the majority of archaeological features related to religion is concentrated over there.

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 1500 CE

Region: Erlitou Yanshi, Henan

Region tags: China, Henan Province, Erlitou village, Yanshi city

The site of Erlitou is located south of the Luo River. It covers the modern-day village Erlitou and overlaps with a few other neighbouring villages under the Yanshi city.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: IA CASS (Institute of Archaeology, Chinese Academy of Social Science 中国社会科学院考古研究所). 2014. Erlitou: 1999–2006. Beijing: Wenwu Chubanshe (in Chinese)
- Source 2: Allan, S., 2007. Erlitou and the formation of Chinese civilization: Toward a new paradigm. *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 66(2), pp.461-496.
- Source 3: Zhang, C., Pollard, A., Rawson, J., Huan, L., Liu, R., & Tang, X. (2019). China's major Late Neolithic centres and the rise of Erlitou. *Antiquity*, 93(369), 588-603. doi:10.15184/aqy.2019.63

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/main>
- Source 1 Description: The official website of the Erlitou museum (also known as the Museum of the Xia Dynasty) is extremely useful for understanding the material culture of Erlitou and related subjects. It does not only include many well-known artefacts of Erlitou (<https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/zhenpin>), but also 3D exhibition for the whole museum (<https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/chenzhan/c/53>).

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Some parts of the site were looted before the first scientific excavation which took place around 1950s.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: From 1959 to now

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Erlitou excavation

Notes: Because of the importance of the site, Institute of Archaeology Chinese Academy of Social Science set up a special work station at Erlitou, called Erlitou Station.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: The site of Erlitou is located in the valley of the Yi and Luo rivers, both of which are branches of the Yellow River. It is also surrounded by various mountains, including Song Mt in southeast, Mang Mt in northeast and Zhongtiao and Xiao Mt in northwest.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Mound
- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Notes: These features are primarily associated with daily life at Erlitou, since agriculture was the most important.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The ceremonial section is mostly located in the northern part of the site. Erlitou was also one of the earliest urban sites in China. So the place and the urban fabric probably overlapped.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

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↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: They are modern villiages.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Mainly for tourism or excavation purposes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Some building foundations appear circular or oval whereas others appear rectangular.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: Archaeologists have discovered all of the features above (mound, clearing, water channel, purposefully placed plants)

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: From radiocarbon dates and excavation stratigraphy, their constructions and reconstructions involved multiple stages.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: They involve multiple stages based on the stratigraphy and radiocarbon dates.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Many of these features probably belong to the same ceremonial section or the same palace.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

Notes: Worshipping ancestors has been always important practice since Neolithic so it is probably also true for Eritou.

– Sacrificial

Notes: Animal and human sacrifices have been found at Eritou.

– Social

Notes: It could be part of social organization.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on the radiocarbon dates probably yes.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: It looks like a palace was built over the old palace. So it is reasonable to assume that some parts of the palace were repaired before abandonment.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: It is difficult to say. Some palaces or structures were destroyed for new buildings but a few others show burning features.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

– As the result of pillage

– Other [specify]: Probably all of these factors can be found at Erlitou but no text helps to testify them.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: There are some modern reconstruction at Erlitou for tourist purposes but the whole site is not reconstructed.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes. From object decorations, one can see imitations of various animals. They were not naturalistic forms but rather abstract. This could be linked to supernatural beings.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This cannot be answered with text. But interestingly, very few remains show human or semi-human forms at Erlitou.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes. But without ancient DNA analysis, it is difficult to tell potential relatedness among individuals. Also worshipping ancestors at Erlitou is a projection of later behaviour during the late Shang period.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: Based on the later oracle bones, the kings and religious specialists (Zhenren 贞人) could have overlapped.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not. Erlitou was the largest settlement in the Yi-Luo valley so it was able to support

these constructions.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: No texts have been discovered at Eritou.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Some may be constructed for convenient access to rivers or wells.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: For example, some altars or mounds probably belong to a larger palace or ceremonial structure.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The size of houses varies, indicating some level of hierarchy.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 10000

Notes: This is Palace No.1 at Erlitou.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Notes: Most of them were made by rammed earth.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Rammed earth

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some circular iconography could be associated with eyes.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The turquoise dragon would be one of the best examples at Eritou.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A large number of tombs have been found at Eritou, though it is not entirely a cemetery.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: not completely sure but based on the later oracle bones it seems that there existed a long tradition for worshipping ancestors in the Central Plains.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Previous contents can be found in elite tombs.

↳ Cannibalism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: Buried with previous objects such as jades or bronzes.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– Yes

↳ How many humans are present:

– Number of human sacrifices:: 10

Notes: It varies from tomb to tomb.

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

–Other [specify]: It is difficult to tell the identity of these human sacrifices since they do not own any objects and no DNA analysis is published.

↳ Animal:

– Yes

↳ How many animals are present:

– Number of animals:: 5

Notes: It varies between tombs.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: It is very likely that the objects buried in the lower-elite or ordinary people's tombs were possessed by them during their lifetime. Those objects such as bronze ritual vessels were also likely used before entering into the deposition, although this is yet to be verified by scientific analysis in the future. Some bronze weapons and tools, in accordance with their alloying composition, were not made for practical use. They might be made for just display or burial purposes.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: A number of tombs are excavated with jades, bronzes, lacquer, turquoises, or high-quality ceramics/bone artifacts.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary people were often buried with a few pieces of ceramics.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Ivory, proto-porcelain or white pottery (made with relatively higher temperature and clay with better quality, likely originated in south China).

↳ Other

–Yes [specify]: Pottery is the most prevalent type of grave good at Erlitou. Except for the types of objects mentioned above, in a few cases were also discovered wooden objects.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is very likely but no clan sign or other evidence has been found. Ancient DNA analysis may reveal this as well in the future.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: Some tombs are often found around the palatial section of Erlitou. Their bodies were sometimes arranged in certain posture or directions.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: NA

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Such as the turquoise dragon, if it truly represents supernatural beings.

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: dogs, cattle, sheep/goats

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Adults

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

↳ Children

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves

– Field doesn't know

↳ Elites

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Not that I can think of

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: like medium- or poor-quality pottery

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: NA

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably in the large houses/palaces.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– Field doesn't know

Divination through human communication:

– Field doesn't know

Divination through animal-behavior:

– Field doesn't know

Divination through non-living material:

– Bones

Notes: e.g., burning animal bones

Other

– Other [specify]: NA

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: NA

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: NA

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: More likely to be males but this cannot be testified without text.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some of them could be the ruling class, considering the importance of religious activities. This is certainly true at Anyang.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes since the whole society was hierachical.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely as many large house could be multi-functional, including mass gathering for community service (e.g., distribution of food).

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Li Jaang. Erlitou: The Making of a Secondary State and a New Sociopolitical Order in Early Bronze Age China. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-022-09173-9>.

Reference: Sarah Allen. rlitou and the formation of Chinese civilization: Toward a new paradigm. *Journal of Asian Studies*, 66(2) doi: [doi: 10.1017/S002191180700054X](https://doi.org/10.1017/S002191180700054X).

Reference: Li Liu, Xingcan Chen. *The Archaeology of China*. Cambridge University Press. isbn: 9780521643108.

Reference: Li Liu. Rethinking Erlitou: legend, history and Chinese archaeology. *Antiquity*, 81(313) doi: 10.1017/S0003598X00095983.

Reference: Gideon Shelach-Lavi. *The Archaeology of Early China*. Cambridge University Press. isbn: 9780521196895.

Reference: Jinpeng Du. 偃师二里头遗址祭祀遗存的发现与研究 The sacrifice remains at Erlitou. doi: <http://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotai-ZYWW201904008.htm>.

Reference: Guoliang Chen. 二里头文化的占卜制度初探——以二里头遗址近年出土卜骨为例 The divination system at Erlitou -- a case study of the oracle bones at Erlitou.

Reference: Chi Zhang. China's major Late Neolithic centres and the rise of Erlitou. *Antiquity*, 93(369) doi: 10.15184/aqy.2019.63.